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Research Article

A COMPARATIVE RESEARCH OF FIXATION VERSUS NON-FIXATION TECHNIQUES WITH REFERENCE TO INFLUENCE ON OUTCOMES

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Abstract:

Objective: The objective of this study to compare mesh fixation with non-fixation and its influence on results.

Methods: The time period of this research was between November 2016 to November 2018 at Aziz Fatima Hospital, Faisalabad. The participants were followed up for two years. Two groups were made for the participants. In the first group, metal non-absorbable tackers were used for carrying out the mesh fixation. While in the second group, fixation of mesh was not carried out. All the participants were followed up at 6, 12, 18 and 24 months.

Results: Total patients enrolled in this study were 63. Group – I and II contain 32 (50.7%) and 31 (49.2%) patients respectively. In group 1 ($P > 0.05$), urinary retention was more frequent whereas, in group – II, reoccurrence was frequent ($P > 0.05$). The mean pain score in group I and II was (4.7 ± 0.683) and (4.1 ± 0.860) respectively.

Conclusion: In a non-fixation group, there don't observe a remarkable increase in urinary retention and repetition. However, the pain was remarkably low in this group. Non-fixation should be favored over mesh fixation as it a suitable technique for total extraperitoneal mesh hernioplasty.

Keywords: Fixation, Non-fixation, Mesh, Hernioplasty and Extraperitoneal.

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INTRODUCTION:

One of the frequently faced issues in surgical care is a hernia. For primary inguinal hernia and repeated inguinal hernia repair, laparoscopic hernia repair is now considered a suitable method. Laparoscopic has set a new path for surgeons [1]. Now total extraperitoneal (TEP) repair is suggested by most of the surgeons. It is suitable because it offers a minimum incidence of visceral up of peritoneal cavity [2]. Open hernia and TEP are compared. TEP proved more suitable due to earlier recovery, minimum chances of urinary retention, less postoperative discomfort and shorter duration of hospital stay [3]. Mesh can be fixed into place with tackers and can be placed without fixation [4]. It is indicated by many studies that suitable choice is non-fixation. It offers less chance of repetition. When it is compared to tacker fixation, it is useful because of improved life quality, less duration of operation and less chronic groin discomfort [5, 6]. The objective of the current study was to make comparison fixation and non-fixation of mesh in TEP inguinal hernia repair in terms of postoperative pain and repetition rate.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The time period of this research was between November 2016 to November 2018 at Aziz Fatima Hospital, Faisalabad. The participants were followed up for two years. Two groups were made for the participants. In the first group, metal non-absorbable tackers were used for carrying out the mesh fixation. While in the second group, fixation of mesh was not carried out. All the participants were followed up at 6, 12, 18 and 24 months. VAS was used for the measurement of pain score. For examining any contribution and chronic groin pain, the patients were followed up at 0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2 years. All the operations were carried out by a single surgical team. Patients identified with a reducible incomplete inguinal hernia were selected in succeeding order. These patients were between 16 – 70 years of age. These patients were excluded who were found with

pediatric hernias or large complete, blocked and strangulated hernias. Ethical review committee approval was also taken. General anesthesia and Spinal Anesthesia was used for operating the patients. The patients were placed in supine position. While on the opposite side to a hernia, there stood a camera assistant and operating surgeon. An incision of size 12mm was built that was inferior to the umbilicus. A small incision was used for the opening of an identified rectus sheath. There developed a muscle space for a 10mm cannula after retraction of rectus. By means of the port, telescope was introduced. Between umbilicus and pubic symphysis and above pubic symphysis, two working ports of size 5mm were introduced under vision in the midline. Identification regarding the internal side of the deep inguinal ring was made. In order to indicate and separate inguinal canal contents, peritoneum was reflected laterally. A 6X4 inch polypropylene mesh was placed. It was placed in a way that hernia defect was covered. In order to fix the mesh, two staples were used. One staple was at the Cooper ligament and the other above the anterior superior iliac spine. After the operation, the patient was given with three injections of the first-generation cephalosporin. The next day, the patient was allowed to go home.

RESULTS:

Total patients enrolled for this study were 63. Group – I and II contain 32 (50.7%) and 31 (49.2%) patients respectively. In group 1 ($P > 0.05$), urinary retention was more frequent whereas, in group – II, reoccurrence was frequent ($P > 0.05$). The mean pain score in group I and II was (4.7 ± 0.683) and (4.1 ± 0.860) respectively. In group – II, chances of recurrence were more frequent (1); whereas, in Group – I, chances of urinary reflection were more frequent (5). But both these variables were not remarkable statistically. Within the first day of surgery, urinary retention occurred. It was controlled by passing a Foleys Catheter. It was removed afterwards. Chronic urinary retention was not observed in any patient.

Table: Gender, Hernia Side and Type and Complications Stratification

Variables		Fixation (32)		Non-Fixation (31)	
		Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Gender	Male	28	87.5	28	90.3
	Female	4	12.5	3	9.7
Side of Hernia	Right	22	68.8	10	31.2
	Left	21	67.7	10	32.3
Type of Hernia	Direct	6	18.7	6	19.4
	Indirect	26	81.3	25	80.6
Complications	Urinary Retention	5	15.6	4	12.9
	Hernia Recurrence	0	0	1	3.2

DISCUSSION:

No remarkable dissimilarity in pain was observed statistically by irregular control trials [4]. Postoperative pain is lesser in TEP hernia repair after comparison of transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) against TEP [7]. Use of trackers in specific patients is suggested by a trial spanning over ten years [8]. Another such study indicated that in young patients, early postoperative groin pain was more frequent [9].

Fibrin glue can be used instead of trackers. It reduces inflammation and irritation and as a result diminishes postoperative discomfort [10, 11]. Another secure and efficient technique is re-surgery with mesh fixation in those cases where the mesh is not fixed [12]. Need for trackers can be replaced by a newer self-gripping mesh [13]. In children above five years of age, Laparoscopic TEP with mesh placement can be carried out. It does not offer any danger of contribution [14]. The leaning

curve of the laparoscopic mesh is lengthy but it is secure and has low repetition in expert hands [15]. After laparoscopic inguinal hernia repair, the incidence of urinary retention is found in 1% to 2% of patients [16]. The incidence of urinary retention in our research exists in 12% to 15% of patients. This is more than that has been mentioned in history. Age or older urinary issues may be responsible for it. A mobile mesh may destroy into urinary bladder [17].

CONCLUSION:

Between the two groups, no remarkable difference was found in the recurrence and urinary retention. There observed a remarkable decrease in pain in case of non-fixation of mesh.

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